

Deliverable 3.1

REPORT ON FUNDERS ENGAGEMENT AND FORUM AGENDA

FOODPATHS WP3

Report on funders engagement and forum agenda

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1. Introduction and background

The FOODPathS WP3 follows the overall aim of “Building a Food System co-funding network and aligning funding strategies”. This implies thinking and working towards a transformation from established funding schemes and designs towards more co-creation based funding approaches respecting the needs of public authorities and researchers as well as providing the necessary room needed for stakeholder engagement and participation following the idea of a systems approach. The main target group of this WP are thus funders, both public and private, on regional and national scales and from different sectors of the food system.

The WP is structured in 4 tasks:

Task number	Task description	Organisations involved
3.1	Mapping of public and private potential co-funders and engagement scheme (M1 – M18)	Leader: FZJ; Contributors: AU, IRWIR PAN, Cariplo, EFC, SeAMK, ZonMw
3.2	Funders forum (M3 – M24)	Leader: ZonMw; Contributors: AU, IRWIR PAN, Cariplo, EFC, FZJ, SeAMK
3.3	Aligning transnational call procedures and funding strategies in a system approach (M6 – M30)	Leader: AU; Contributors: Cariplo, EFC, IRWIR PAN, FZJ, SeAMK, ZonMw
3.4	Preparing for a branded network of SSFS-Partnership projects (M16 – M30)	Leader: FZJ; Contributors: AU, SeAMK, ZonMw, IRWIR PAN

This Deliverable is focussing on the first two tasks. Task 3.1 is about mapping public and private co-funders, who are involved in various elements of sustainable food systems in order to understand which organisations could become part of the future funders network of the Partnership. The second task 3.2 aims at starting interaction with and between the various (mapped and un-mapped) funders in an open environment of a series of online and physical interactive events, the so called “funders forum”, to enable knowledge and information exchange, prepare for future funding activities and prepare for transformation through co-creation and a systems approach. The co-creation process and the systems approach will be covered intensively in the different funders forum events.

FOODPathS is a “network of networks” and also for WP3 it is imperative to have a good geographical coverage as well as a diversity of actors represented in the WP3 team itself. In table 1 the WP3 team composition is shown. Seven partners from seven countries are involved, who represent networks of

Associated network	FOODPathS partner	Representatives	Type of organisation	Type of network partners	Country
CORE Organic network (27 partners in 19 countries)	Aarhus University - International Centre for Research in Organic Food Systems (AU-ICROFS)	Ivana Trkulja Merete Studnitz	Research Organisation	Public partners	Denmark
Fondazione Cassa di Risparmio Delle Provincie Lombardie (Cariplo)		Valentina Amorese Sara Scalabrin	Philanthropic Organisation	Philanthropic partners	Italy
BIOEAST	Institute of Rural and Agricultural Development of the Polish Academy of Sciences (IRWIR PAN)	Barbara Wieliczko Aleksandra Pawłowska Pawel Chmielinski	Research Organisation	Public partners	Poland
Philanthropy Europe Association (Philea)		Giulia Lombardi	Philanthropic Organisation	Philanthropic partners	Belgium

SUSFOOD2 network (26 partners from 15 countries)	Research Center Jülich (FZJ)	Nikola Hassan Frank Hensgen	Research Organisation	Public partners	Germany
ERIAFF network of regions (54 members and 39 observers)	Seinäjoki University of Applied Sciences (SeAMK)	Terhi Junkkari Karri Kallio	Higher Education	Regional, public partners	Finland
Joint Programming Initiative a Healthy Diet for a Healthy Life (JPI HDHL, 28 partners from 19 countries)	The Netherlands Organisation for Health Research and Development (ZonMw)	Jasmina van Driel Bernadette Conrads	Funding Organisation	Public partners	Netherlands

Table 1 – Associated networks in work package 3

When reaching out to funders, the above connections to the associated networks of partner organisations were the first routes for contacts. Additionally, all other FOODPathS partners and their associated networks were contacted as well as the SCAR SWG FS members in order to identify additional funding organisations.

2. Ways of engagement and methodology

The aim of engaging a wide range of usual and not so usual funders was to build up an extensive network of potential funders who will become involved in the future Sustainable Food Systems Partnership.

The main target groups for engagement were:

- 1) the associated network partners (see above. 'Table 1 – associated networks in WP3),
- 2) SCAR SWG FS contacts and
- 3) all other contacts derived via broad communication and recruitment (e.g. via the FOODPathS partners and their networks and communication channels).

The main ways of engagement for the different activities described hereunder can be summarized as follows:

- Funders network and map: general email, later also FOODPathS social media channels and website, dedicated survey
- Interview series: personal contact via email/phone and video-conferences with interviewees
- Funders Forum: information via email and FOODPathS social media channels and website, online registration

From the very beginning, we took an open and transparent communication approach. We shared the mandate and purpose of FoodPathS and our work package, and the nature of our work, emphasising the role of the FOODPathS project to develop and test a prototype SFS Partnership and to establish a wide funders network with organisations that can become involved in the future SFSP. . We contacted potential participants via email, and shared information through partners' outlets (e.g. offering webinars about FOODPathS to the associated networks by SUSFOOD2 and CORE Organic). We also created a dedicated leaflet (Annex I) for WP3, which was shared via social media. For all funders, both public and private, it was important not only to spread general information about the project and future partnership, but to be very clear and concrete about expectations and offerings associated with participation in the funders forums and in the future partnership.

2.1. Funders network and map

2.1.1. Aim and concept

The aim of the funders network and map is to gather and showcase a group of interested funders who are willing to shape and prepare the future funding in the Partnership. A survey (link at the end of this paragraph) was used to collect contacts and the target groups to populate the network and map. Initial contact information was collected by the WP3 lead from the 3 main groups as stated in the paragraph at the beginning of this chapter). Within the survey, the network and map are explained as follows:

“The Network is meant as group of funders who are interested and motivated to get involved in the preparation towards the future funding within the Partnership on Sustainable Food Systems. All funders are invited to join. In the Network we aim to create a place for dialogue, sharing of information, practices, needs, visions and concerns. We will offer several events for active exchange (funders forum, mainly online) and will prepare some recommendations and guidelines.

The Map will be displayed on the FOODPathS website and will give basic information about interested funders for the future Partnership on Sustainable Food Systems. Being part of the map is no formal commitment and completely voluntary.”

The following questions are asked in the survey:

- Funding entity information
- Type of entity (governmental/ non-governmental)
- Source of funding (public/ private)
- Funding level (geographically)
- Funding priorities (along the 4 thematic R&I areas of the SRIA)
- Logo of organisation
- Approval for joining network and/or map

The survey remains open and is accessible online: https://www.surveymonkey.de/r/FOODPathS_Funders

2.1.2. Results

The results of the mapping will be displayed in Deliverable 2.1 (Report of Mapping Results) and thus, only briefly summarized at this point.

The first contact actions to recruit organisations for the network and map took place at the end of September 2022. Follow up communications took place until the beginning of December 2022, when the FoodPathS project website was launched. At that point, it became possible to refer to the FOODPathS website and the dedicated subpage for the Network of funders and map, and thus, more broad outreach was possible. Figure 1 shows the number of responses to the survey over time.

Figure 1

At the time of writing, (March 2023), 40 funding organisations have joined the Network and 37 funding organizations are displayed on the Map (some chose not to be displayed on the map). 19 countries are represented (see figure 2). The majority of organisations are of governmental nature (73%), 16% are NGOs and 11% are cluster organisations. 15 regional actors are involved (mainly from Belgium, Italy, Spain, Ireland and Finland) and 3 foundations. The dedicated webpage for the Funders network and interactive map (with various filtering options) can be found here: <https://www.foodpaths.eu/map-of-funders/>

Countries and number of entities per country in Funders Map

Figure 2

2.1.3. Discussion

The feedback received towards the survey and the willingness to join the network and map clearly shows that mainly “trusted” and previously established contacts were reached (see figure 1 and timepoint of subscriptions mainly during the first waves of contactings, which addressed target audiences of associated network partners and SCAR SWG FS contacts). A challenge and next focus of our work is to further widen the map of funders, beyond these trusted contacts, with more countries, more regions, a higher number of relevant private actors, e.g. by identifying philanthropic

organisations, finance sectors (banks) as well as private funders (via notably Philea, FoodDrinkEurope, CONFAGRICOLTURA etc.).

Since the timeline of the CSA FOODPathS overlaps with the preparatory phase of the Partnership itself, we experienced some confusion about the Funders network and map and the relation with the Partnership consortium.

The interactive map will be a living map until the start of the future partnership, but it remains unclear how to make best use of the network and map along the lifetime of the P-SFS consortium (what could be their medium/long-term purpose?). At this point a first estimation of how many of the Funders network members are also integrated into the consortium of the future Partnership shows a ~70% overlap. This also implies that 30% of contacted funders have not taken the step to join the Partnership. A future next objective is to engage about this and learn why..

2.2. Interview series

2.2.1. Background and objectives

To prepare for the first online funders forum event in the last quarter of 2022 and for the physical funders forum in the first quarter of 2023, a series of interviews was conducted with a variety of selected funders. The interviews were meant to serve on the one hand as inspiration for the dialogue on the integration of food systems approach into funding practices and on the other hand to gain insight into how the FOODPathS consortium can support funders moving forward into the SFS partnership.

The specific objective of the interviews were:

- To collect first ideas from funders on possible ways to align funding strategies and adapt the funding landscape to make it easier to fund interdisciplinary, multi-actor and systems oriented research around sustainable food systems, in other words to develop innovative funding approaches
- To gain insight into what the FOODPathS consortium can do for funders (what are their needs) to be guided towards the future SFS Partnership

A guidance note that was prepared for structuring the interviews can be found in Annex II.

2.2.2. Results and discussion

Between October 2022 and February 2023, 16 interviews were conducted with public and private funding bodies from 11 countries (10 countries in Europe and Canada). The questions posed to the interviewees were divided over five categories, including: current situation, good practices and improvement, future funding, partnership involvement/interest and other various questions.

See an anonymised list below. An overview of the questions and summaries of answers to each question can be found in Annex III.

Belgium – public funding body, regional

Canada – RPO on behalf of member public funding body, national

Estonia – public funding body, national

Finland – public funding body, regional

France – public funding body, regional

Germany – public funding bodies, national

Italy – public and private funding bodies, national and regional

Netherlands – public funding body, national

Poland – public funding body, national

Romania – RPO on behalf of member public funding body, national

Sweden – public funding body, national

Switzerland – public funding body, national

An interview was also conducted with an international expert body on Sustainable Food Systems.

Main results

The structure of the quadruple helix was often brought up in the sense that it is crucial to involve government, science and academia, non-governmental and private sector stakeholders in the funding mechanism. Most of the regional funding organisations and foundations emphasised the need to create synergy between local traditions/ local knowledge and new knowledge and R&I to achieve added value. This implies also the involvement of small actors and (local) stakeholders on EU level. Also important to develop a 'common language' in the food system, since a lot of different actors are involved. This can be achieved by for example creating a good practice manual for farmers and others in the agricultural process.

Furthermore, several organisations indicated that a long term transformation also needs a long term approach in funding to reach the end-consumer or build new knowledge and it might be valuable to think about follow-up projects or investing in connecting projects with each other. The efforts to apply for funding should be as low as possible, decreasing bureaucracy for application and reporting. The type of calls, besides classical transnational projects, that worked well in the past and were brought up during the interviews to be considered for future calls are knowledge hubs, living labs (long funding period), accelerators, incubators and the funding of health charity projects. One funding organisation mentioned the use of a real common pot, which addresses the challenge given in some calls to strictly follow the ranking list, but depending on the modalities it might be a delicate subject to fund other countries' research projects with national money (in the co-fund instrument a mixed mode for funding might be applied, using a real and virtual common pot, but in this case only EU money will be used for the real common pot for gap filling).

In addition, a lot of the interviewees indicated that a holistic or systems approach is needed, also to overcome funding programmes that act in silos. Several good examples were under the ERA-Nets (f.e FACCE ERA-GAS (monitoring and mitigation of greenhouse gases), SusAn (ERA-Net on Sustainable Animal Production Systems) and SYSTEMIC (Knowledge Hub on Food and Nutrition Security with JPI HDHL, JPI FACCE and JPI OCEANS)). Another example is the multidisciplinary approach in a resilience program in Romania where collaboration was mandatory between five separately funded projects in the areas of health, food and soil.

Lastly, it is important to communicate and evaluate the perceived outcomes of funded projects with the end-users or target group, depending on the project. To this end one interviewee also mentioned the importance of dissemination activities to policy makers and putting more emphasis on the science-to-policy intersection.

Interesting quotes

Some quotes were selected from the interviews and provided here to illustrate the richness of ideas and insights that came out of the interviews:

'Indigenous population should also benefit from the research'

'Long-term development agreements with stakeholders would be good, as well as long term thematic plans with long term funding. This would focus development work.'

'Estonia is a small country compared to others but we have a strong record participating in many ERA-Nets. For us the added value of collaboration on European level is clear. Not only does it bring immense economic advantage to pool resources, but our research community gets new international contacts and can gain capacities and expertise not available on national level. At the same time, others can profit from our expertise and collaboration.'

'There is already a lot of information and knowledge created in different EU-projects... how to scale them up and learn from each other?'

'How SFSP and innovation could be linked to legislation preparation?'

'The link between university research centres and territorial networks allows for a qualified point of view, and this would lead to greater transmissibility to the productive sector'

'For us, as funder of industry actors in Flanders, valorisation is key. Our experience from Partnerships in FP7/8 (ERA-Nets and ERA-Net Cofunds) shows that many companies used this as entry point to the European arena. The network that opened up for them was a huge added value!

We also observe a trend in projects evolving from being rather scientific towards more applied R&I and that is interesting for us. We hope that more funders that fund industry will join in order to have strong industry participation in the future projects.'

'One of the greatest limits of supporting food system transformation relay in the difficulties in communicating the results. There clearly are great practices already existing, but many of us do not know them. Results tend to be communicated only to peers or closed stakeholders. There should be special channels to communicate the results so that they can spread and we could all benefit from them avoiding replication of efforts.'

‘You can go to a restaurant to get a meal. If you go alone, you can have your meal quietly and quickly and after an hour you will be back home. If you go in a group, it will take longer to order the food, maybe you will get food that you would not have chosen yourself, you will talk with some people during the meal and the meal will take longer. After three hours you will be back home, and you have had a meal and a completely different experience from when you went to the restaurant alone. So really, you can reach the aim two ways, but we can agree that it’s not the same; eating alone as eating with a lot of other people but eating together is much more complicated.’

2.3. First Funders Forum – online 29 November 2022

2.3.1. Objectives and outline

The first FOODPathS Funders Forum was held online on the 29th of November 2022. It was meant as a first step in a series of engagement events to bring together funders from different countries and also different sectors related to food systems.

The objectives of the First Funders Forum were:

- To share information about FOODPathS and the development of the SFS Partnership: clarify the different roles, timelines and what can be expected
- To generate ideas to inspire future funding mechanisms in the SFS partnership to be able to address transdisciplinary, food systems oriented research topics and collect experiences (good practices at various levels)
- To generate enthusiasm of funders to join the network, funders map and the future SFS Partnership

The first part of the funders forum consisted of presentations and the second part of an interactive group session. Daniela Lueth (EC) provided a clear presentation on how the Partnership is embedded in the policy context and what is expected from Commission’s side. She also gave a timeline with most important milestones and some information about the stated commitments so far and the foreseen composition of partners in the future consortium. Hugo De-Vries (INRAE), project coordinator of FOODPathS, explained how the project’s activities will create the prototype of the future Partnership. He outlined that the role of funders is crucial to get and keep the Partnership in motion via joint orchestrated activities internally and externally with other Partnerships. He also stressed the importance of identifying the trade-offs of each of the measures to be proposed and how to better address them.

Nikola Hassan (Jülich) fine-tuned how the project is building a Food System’s co-funding network to connect stakeholders and align funding strategies that represent the struggles and ideas from all the sectors involved.

An overview of the funders forum agenda can be found in Annex IV.

The 3 presentations were followed by an interactive session, where the attendees were assigned to smaller breakout rooms of 8-10 people. Each of the groups was given the following assignment:

“Imagine we are in 2033 (future in 10 years). The Partnership SFS has been a great success and R&I played an important role to enable the transformation of our Food Systems to be sustainable, healthy and resilient and supporting a healthy and thriving European population. Please answer one, two or all of the following questions:

- What changes are necessary - with regard to funding of research - to support this transformation through transdisciplinary research? (step out of your comfort zone, envisage the ideal world, think in innovative ways)
- To determine what impact the SFS partnership will have had in 10 years time please try to answer the following: What does “impact” mean for you? What does it mean for a transnational collaboration? What are points in the funding cycle where we can steer for impact?
- Please provide examples of research projects with a multi/inter/transdisciplinary, wide (systems) focus that could contribute to this vision (think of different levels, national, regional, international and different types of projects, e.g. living labs, knowledge hubs, classic research projects and others)”

The active participation of the attendees led to the generation of ideas to inspire future funding mechanisms in the SFS partnership and food systems-oriented research topics while collecting experiences and good practices at various levels.

2.3.2. Main results

At the end of the forum participants seemed to have more clarity on the differences between FOODPathS and the SFS Partnership. Another key result was that an open dialogue was initiated through which funders, but also other stakeholders, can start openly discussing, debating and co-creating future funding approaches that can really serve food systems research which can in turn drive food systems transformation.

The forum also provided an appropriate context for interaction where attendees had the chance to get their questions answered and provide their points of view. The questions and answers were combined in an overall Q&A document provided to the attendees after the event. The Q&A document was developed with valuable input from Daniela Luth from EC DG RTD and consisted of four distinct sections: difference between FOODPathS and the Partnership, explanation of the role and activities of WP 3 of FOODPathS, an overview of relevant links and notes on categories of countries and partners.

The Q&A, all the presentations and a recording of the Funders Forum can be accessed and downloaded from the FOODPathS website: <https://www.foodpaths.eu/resource/funders-forum-resources/>.

The main results of the interactive working groups are provided below:

Q1 - What changes are necessary - with regard to funding of research - to support this transformation through transdisciplinary research:

- There seems to be a discrepancy between a transdisciplinary, systemic approach in research and the way funders and ministries provide research funding, which is still too much along sectoral silos. For this partnership not only agri-food or R&D oriented ministries should be involved but also health and education.
- Stakeholders need to be involved more in food systems research along the whole research chain, including consumers, citizens (especially young people) and private sector stakeholders such as SMEs (not only large corporations) and farmers.
- Researchers from different sectors and focusing on different parts of the food value chain need to work together (i.e. social sciences, humanities, from production to consumption).
- Importance of focusing on consumers and children
- Importance of multi-actor approach
- Need to draft impact pathway/Theory of Change
- Important to have follow up or even continuation of projects
- Need to create synergies between European and national funds
- Dissemination should get increased budget
- Use what is available and build on that: living and policy labs, knowledge hubs, practical expertise. There is a real need for funding co-creative research
- Nutrition needs more attention
- Coordination between partnerships is necessary for impact in the whole food system
- More flexibility in funding mechanisms is needed, at least for smaller projects

Q2 and Q3 on impact and interesting examples/good practices:

- Impact means different things: coordinating the action well, impacting on real world challenges, moving towards a sustainable food system
- Impact is about influencing the food chain and reaching a more coherent public policy around food, with a science/evidence base
- Impact measurement is important, but the Partnership should not lose itself in KPIs but dare to pursue long-term, ambitious goals
- Impact should be beneficial to citizens
- A measurement of success could be whether funders want to stay in the Partnership after 10 years
- Local relevance is important – create knowledge that can be used for societal challenges
- Synergies also need to be created between member states to increase impact at supra-national level
- Motivate researchers to step out of their comfort zone

2.3.3. Discussion

There was great interest in the forum evidenced by the attendance of 120 people – we feel this was partially because of the fact that it was unclear what the difference was between FOODPathS and the Partnership and in how and within what timeline the partnership would develop and partially because funders are eager to work together to change the funding landscape to enable food system transformation. In addition, there was also great willingness and enthusiasm to critically look at funding mechanisms and approaches and have an open dialogue on what is needed for change. However, the reality is challenging in the current funding landscape and funders still continue to operate within their sectors and the funding landscape is quite compartmentalised.

2.4. Second Funders Forum – in Brussels 8th February 2023

2.4.1. Objectives and outline of the event

The second FOODPathS Funders Forum was held on the 8th of February 2023. It was envisaged as a next step to dive deeper into what food systems funding approaches could or should entail at the level of the call text, evaluation and impact.

The specific objectives of this second Funders Forum were:

- To obtain updates from different actors regarding the process towards the Sustainable Food Systems Partnership (a.o. EC DG RTD, Proposal Coordinator ANR)
- To share and collect examples of Food Systems funding approaches
- To test a Food Systems funding approach on real-life topics

The first part of the funders forum consisted of presentations and Q&A sessions dedicated to the development of the Partnership and the Partnership consortium formation. The part after this was focused on the discussion around good practices and inspiring examples of food systems funding and research approaches. After this, an interactive group session took place. An overview of the funders forum agenda can be found in Annex V.

[Daniela Lüth](#), from EC DG RTD, provided an insightful presentation on how the SFS Partnership relates to the FOODPathS CSA project, the expected timeline and the distinction between internal and external calls. [Gilles Ferron](#), from ANR, explained what the Partnership Consortium building process entails and the expected next steps. He also introduced the core group of the Consortium and provided insights into the results of the survey that was conducted in cooperation with FOODPathS, including geographical coverage of interested partners. Finally, he shared an overview of the preliminary work package structure and next steps. [Frank Hensgen](#), from Juelich, provided the audience with 4 examples of food systems funding and research approaches: FOODIVERSE (diversifying sustainable and organic food systems), SmartDairy (assessing challenges, innovations and solutions of climate smart dairy), AlgaeBrew (microalgae to transform brewery waste into feed and fertiliser) and SYSTEMIC (Knowledge Hub on Food and Nutrition Security). After the three presentations, Nikola Hassan from Juelich led the discussion with project partners (Terhi Junkkari from SeAMK/ERIAFF, Giulia Lombardi from Philea, Ivana Trkulja from AU-ICROFS/CORE Organic, and Jasmina van Driel from ZonMw/JPI HDHL) who shared their experiences in food systems approaches, highlighting specific points of attention such as the importance of inclusion of new and innovative funders from regions and foundations, which can act as accelerators of transformation towards sustainable food systems.

The interactive afternoon session, exclusively for live participants, primarily entailed a discussion on a food system conceptual model. This model aims to unpack the food system approach by 1) exploring the impacts of change across the full system, 2) capturing potential trade-offs between domains, and 3) recognising the complexities and dynamism of the food system.

Following the introductions of the model, the participants were challenged to consider the three levels of implementation – call text, proposal evaluation and impact level – that formed the basis of the interactive session. The participants were split into 3 groups and encouraged to think outside their comfort zones to come up with ideas for funding strategies and mechanisms that could enable real food systems-oriented, transdisciplinary research. Each group covered each of the three levels during the session, to ensure a rich diversity of perspectives and inputs to each level.

A total of 45 participants attended the meeting (both online and physically), representing different sectors and institutions. An overview of the type of institutions represented is provided in the graph below.

Figure 3 - Live and online attendees second funders forum

2.4.2. Main results

One of the main results was that participants had more clarity on the state of play of the SFS Partnership and the status of the Partnership consortium formation. Another key result was that good practices were shared and discussed on food systems funding and research approaches.

Another result was the fact that the forum provided an appropriate context for interaction where attendees had the chance to get their questions answered and provide their points of view. The questions and answers were combined in an overall Q&A document provided to the attendees after the event. The Q&A document was developed with valuable input from Daniela Lüth from EC DG RTD and representatives from the SFS Consortium and consisted of distinct sections. The Q&A document from the first funders forum in November was integrated into this new Q&A document.

All the presentations, a recording of the Funders Forum and the consolidated Q&A document can be accessed and downloaded from the FOODPathS website (<https://www.foodpaths.eu/news-item/funders-met-face-to-face-in-brussels-to-co-create-the-future-sfs-partnership/>).

The main results of the working groups are provided below:

Food Systems (FS) approach in the call text

- Multi-disciplinarity and a multi-actor approach are key
- An food system definition should be included in the call text
- The transition and change towards sustainable and resilient FS systems are not always linear processes to understand and implement and they mean different things to different stakeholders – a Theory of Change approach could be considered
- Connection with the local agenda where the funded project is happening is crucial
- Guidelines for the calls should be assessed from the perspective of funders who have a more generalist perspective, instead of a narrower single-disciplinary perspective
- Considering how to make food system criteria more measurable is also important

Food Systems approach at the proposal evaluation level

- Expert panels need to be able to cover the systems approach
- Different approaches for expert panels possible (having extra experts on systems approach vs. including more diverse experts into one joint group, e.g. experts with systems knowledge, academia, industry, consumer experts, social scientists and different stakeholder representatives = more multi-actor approach also for the expert panel)
- Need to have very clear FS criteria based on a universal definition of the FS

- On the basis of the FS definition the following should be established to enable fair, transparent and measurable evaluation:
 - A list of all the criteria within the FS definition
 - Description of the minimum thresholds for these criteria
 - Allow projects at different scales, e.g. involvement of stakeholders, level of change, level of research (basic to implementation)
 - Think about weighting of criteria
- Supportive guidelines are needed
- The FSA could be used to differentiate between proposals, so that a proposal with a better (or higher degree of) food systems approach should be funded before an otherwise good proposal with less focus on FSA
- Idea to develop some plan/matrix/list to display criteria or formulated as achievements (like potential for transformation/ pathways for impact/change), that the proposal should respond to (to give structure both for applicants and experts/funders)

Food Systems guiding points at the impact level

The main conclusions from this group can be summarized as follows:

- Before starting, a baseline and value chain approach and follow up are key
- Post project monitoring is essential and for a longer period after the project is finished
- True participatory approach – multistakeholder
- Within the partnership the outcomes of the internal calls can be collected and uses as input to the external calls
- Exploitation and investment plans should be mandatory from the onset
- A Theory of Change approach will help to pre-identify impact areas and follow up
- It is essential to build on local realities – research driven by actual societal challenges will generate most impact
- Testing of promising approaches can be done in living and policy labs, before scaling for impact and labs are very appropriate mechanisms for monitoring
- Longer funding horizons also crucial for impact (more than 2 to 3 years)
- Indicators that need to be included at the very least are environment, behavioral change, health and market uptake
- Funding segmentation needs to be overcome by better alignment of funding between different types of funders, letting different kinds of funders work together

2.4.3. Discussion

The physical Funders Forum confirmed that there is great eagerness and willingness to have an open dialogue on changing current funding mechanisms and approaches. However, the transition to a real food systems approach in research is easier said than done. There were several key elements raised, which necessitate a change in mindset and current way of working:

- Funders from different sectors and different types of funders need to work together and align (f.e. health and agro-food oriented funders in one call, or regional funders and national funders in one call)
- Longer funding horizons and longer post-project monitoring and follow-up is needed
- Multistakeholder and participatory approach integrated along the whole funding cycle and research chain, from start to finish and beyond
- Theory of Change approach to be translated into practice
- It is key to build on local realities and to use what is already there rather than reinvent the wheel

The above recommendations can strengthen the HE Partnership SFS outcomes and support the initial aim with which the HE partnerships came to the stage, namely “bring the European Commission and private and/or public partners together to address some of Europe’s most pressing challenges through concerted research and innovation initiatives. By bringing private and public partners together, European Partnerships help to avoid the duplication of investments and contribute to reducing the fragmentation of the research and innovation landscape in the EU.”¹

¹ <https://eufundingoverview.be/funding/european-partnerships-in-horizon-europe-under-horizon-europe>

Annex I – FOODPathS leaflet for funders

How does a Funder contribute to the Partnership?

You will bring your expertise to the conversation that will shape, plan and prepare the **Partnership's framework for the future funding programme**.

Our 3 principles

- supporting high-quality research in Europe and beyond
- enabling dedicated systems and multi-actor approaches
- being inclusive and impact-driven

Our activities

- Creating an open **network of funders** for gathering experiences and expertise
- Organising convenient online **funders' forum events** to promote a transdisciplinary dialogue, raise questions, and share information
- Showcasing the organisations that are interested in joining the network of funders and the extent of their own networks, by regularly updating the **FOODPathS map** on our website

What's in it for you?

As part of our funders' network, you will evaluate opportunities, limitations, best practices and mechanisms that will allow us to align funding strategies and practices.

- Be part of a strong and impactful network of crucial stakeholders, as fellow funders
- Receive the latest news on the Partnership development
- Be able to share experiences, successes and needs with important actors
- Make your vision for the future of the sustainable food systems count
- Show your organisation's commitment to improving food systems

Our partners

Our networks

food|paths

Your expertise will impact the future of EU food systems.

Join our network of funders!

Nikola Hassan
✉ n.hassan@fz-juelich.de
Frank Hensgen
✉ f.hensgen@fz-juelich.de

food|paths

FOODPathS: building the partnership towards sustainable food systems

How to ensure that the future food systems provide **healthy, tasteful, accessible and safe food** for all in a sustainable way?

How to be sure that **all voices are heard**, and all actors included?

What **role can Research and Innovation play** to come up with solutions?

To successfully address these challenges, a long-term strategy designed by different stakeholders from EU, national and regional authorities and the private sector is paramount.

In this context, the European Commission (EC) promotes the creation of the **European Partnership for Sustainable Food Systems (SFS) for People, Planet & Climate**, to be launched in 2024.

The role of FOODPathS

This project aims to offer a concrete pathway, an appropriate operational environment and the necessary tools for the future SFS Partnership. Through the engagement of stakeholders across food systems, the project will create a "Prototype" of how the future Partnership could operate. In detail, FOODPathS will co-design:

- The **Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA)** for the future SFS Partnership, to increase responsiveness to future funding calls.
- The **concepts for co-creation and definitions** that allow FS actors to share a common language for food system partners through defining concepts.
- A **Hub of Food Systems Living Labs** to overcome current fragmentation and show exemplary SFS cases.
- A **Food System Observatory** for monitoring the sustainability performance of food systems in each EU member states.
- **Education and training programs** through a network of higher education institutes working in food systems.
- Future funding mechanisms and strategies that can **maximise the impact of Research and Innovation towards SFS** by gathering experiences and expertise from the Network of Funders.

Funded by the European Union

Annex II - Interview guideline

Introduction

The activities under WP 3 are aimed at building a food system co-funding network and aligning funding strategies. One specific activity focuses on organising open funders dialogues through physical and online events (funders fora). To prepare for the first physical funders forum in the first quarter of 2023 and online funders event in the last quarter of 2022, a series of interviews will be conducted with a variety of selected funders. The interviews are meant to serve on the one hand as inspiration for the dialogue on the development of innovative, and out-of-the-box research funding mechanisms and on the other hand to gain insight into how the FOODPathS consortium can support funders moving forward into the SFS partnership. It is expected that the interviews will also generate input for development of case studies, which can be used to inspire change in the European funding landscape.

Objective of the interviews

- To collect first ideas from funders on possible ways to align funding strategies and adapt the funding landscape to make it easier to fund interdisciplinary, multi-actor and systems oriented research around sustainable food systems, in other words to develop innovative funding approaches
- To gain insight into what the FOODPathS consortium can do for funders (what are their needs) to be guided towards the future SFS Partnership

Before the interview

Prior to conducting the interview, the interviewee needs to have a first understanding of the goal of the interview and the distinction between the CSA FOODPathS and the SFS Partnership. At the start of the interview this should be briefly summarised, to make sure the interviewee is aware of the distinction. When contacting the funders by email for setting the interview appointment, you can draft your own email or use part of the text as was developed for the funders survey. Also ask if they have filled in the funders survey, and make sure not to ask the same questions again (for example under point 4 – are you interested to join the SFS partnership?).

Potential questions

During the main part of the interview one or more questions can be covered. It is recommended you focus on open questions mainly, and use the more closed type of questions under point 1 as a warm up/introduction. This is because at a later stage in the process we will have a follow-up survey which will go into more detail.

- 1) Current situation:
 - In which funding initiatives are you currently involved in? F.e. other HE partnerships such as ERA4Health, ERA-nets, national/regional level etc.
 - For foundations specifically: Are you involved in research programme funding or grant scheme funding or both?
 - What are your current funding mechanisms and regulations with regard to:
 - Type of organisation eligible for funding: research, education, government, private sector/industry, NGO
 - Involvement/integration of stakeholders throughout the research process (f.e. at the JPI HDHL this was made mandatory during one of the latest research calls).
 - Type of call, f.e. classic research call or knowledge hub
 - What type of calls do you have that we might not be aware of?
- 2) Good practices and improvement:
 - What in your view are the strengths and challenges of current funding mechanisms? F.e. think of alignment of funding, common pot funding, type of projects..... etc
 - Question about a good practice, or even better a bad (not so good) practice. Often we find it difficult to talk about this, but these can be extremely valuable for learning. We can indicate to the interviewees that we are planning to organise a workshop or competition on this (best bloopers or failures).
- 3) Future funding: How current funding mechanisms could be best involved in future funding partnership?
 - What elements would an ideal funding landscape need to have in your view, to be able to tackle the food system crisis we currently find ourselves in?

- Have you come across any (innovative) funding mechanisms that specifically support systems/ multi-actor/ multidisciplinary / transdisciplinary approaches (see Annex 1), if so what did or do they look like?
 - Are you involved in other Horizon Europe (HE) Partnerships and if so what do you think the SFS partnership can learn from these regarding funding mechanisms and alignment?
- 4) Partnership involvement:
- Are you interested to join the SFS Partnership and thus our funding network? It is emphasised here that we are just gauging preliminary interest and that you don't need to indicate any definite commitment yet.
 - What do you need from us? What kind of input or support is needed from us which can help you be guided to the partnership?
- 5) Final questions:
- Which other person/organisation do you suggest we also interview, if any?
 - Can you provide us with a short statement or sentence to motivate other funders to become part of the SFS Partnership funding network and interactive map?

The last question is only if you think this is appropriate and relevant for the particular funder. This can also be asked at a later stage.

For each interview, try to cover a variety of questions and cut the interview into separate parts when editing, so that you end up with several short, bite-size clips. Always ask for agreement to record and ask whether (part of) the clip can be posted online. If time allows and you have the opportunity to do a test interview internally, that would be good. Otherwise you can perhaps start with a funder that you already know quite well.

Interview process

There are two options for conducting the interviews, whereby option 1 has preference. If this is not possible due to conflicting agendas or time differences, then option 2 can be used as a backup.

- 1) Through online video-conferencing software such as ZOOM or MS Teams, using the record option (advantages: allows for flexibility; disadvantages: more static background)
- 2) Interviewees answering the questions and having this recorded on their mobile phones (advantages: more interesting/dynamic background possible; disadvantages: does not allow for flexibility, asking for elaboration of answers etc)

Selection of interviewees

A variety of funders will be selected f.e. those which fund only research organisations and those which also fund other types of organisations f.e. private sector. This will allow for capturing a range of views and for comparing different approaches and experiences. Elements such as regional distribution and a mix of large and smaller funders will also be taken into account when selecting funders to interview as well as targeting funders from outside of the EU, from associated countries. In addition, "unusual" suspect funders will be approached, such as philanthropic organisations. Prior to conducting the interviews a candidate list will be developed.

Tentative time line

September 2022 – selection of interviewees and coordinate this amongst WP 3 group and rest of FOODPathS consortium and planning interview dates

October 2022 – conducting interviews (each WP 3 contributor to conduct 2 to 3 interviews)

November 2022 – conducting interviews and editing

December 2022 – first online event (insights generated during interviews can be used as input)

February 2022 – first physical Funders Forum event

Annex III - Summaries of answers interviews

Country	Answer
Public national funder Canada	
Current situation	Research funding based on four pillars: biomedical, clinical, health policy (implementation) and population and public health. Third country, so no benefit from EC funding and data sharing is a delicate issue.
Partnerships	No involvement in the partnerships
Good practices	Funding of indigenous organisations with the aim that the community can benefit from the outcome. Funding of health charity in collaboration with a Dutch funding organisation and the Diabetes foundation.
Public regional funder Belgium	
Current situation	National funder with the mission to stimulate and support activities that are focused on innovation and a stronger entrepreneurship. It helps companies and research centers to accomplish their research and development projects. The eligible partners are enterprises; minimum enterprise needs to apply for funding. Enterprises can involve scientific partners and subcontractors in the project. Funding focuses on Impact. No limitations concerning topics (except weapons and arms). Length of projects funded varies, on international level 1-3 years.
Partnerships	Funder is participating in a number of partnerships namely Urban Transition, Water for All, Clean Energy, Blue Economy and will take part in SFS, PAHW, Agroecology, personalised medicine.
Opportunity	For funders of industry actors, valorization is key. The experience from ERA-Nets and ERA-Net Cofunds shows that many companies used this as entry point to the European arena. The network that opened up for the companies was a huge added value! They also observe a trend in projects evolving from being rather scientific towards more applied R&I which is interesting. They hope that more funders that fund industry will join in order to have strong industry participation in the future projects.
Good practices	Good experiences in SUSFOOD2; Broad topics are preferred, applied topics, industrial topics, ideally participation of at least one industry partner per consortium mandatory. Valorisation of the outcome of the research projects should be part of the whole process cycle, from funding to monitoring.
Improvement	Improvement could be made regarding the point of industry participation and evaluation/appreciation of impact (concerning topics, TRL Levels, evaluation criteria and choice of evaluation experts). Bad experiences in the past: Too narrow scopes in calls, scope too scientific, impact often not as much valued as excellence, experts often purely academic and no industrial background.
Public national funder Estonia	
Current situation	National funder with a long experience in funding research and development projects in the food, fishery and agri-business sector.
Partnerships	Funder has actively participated or is participating in several ERA-NETs (e.g. CoreOrganic, SUSFOOD, EUPHRESKO, C-IPM, FACCE ERA-NET Plus Climate Smart Agriculture), as well as in the Horizon 2020 ERA NET Cofunds (SURPLUS, SusAn, SUSFOOD2, ICRAD), and is involved in EJP One Health and EJP Soil and is a member of the European Agricultural Research Initiative (EURAGRI), member of the Joint Programming Initiative on Agriculture, Food Security and Climate Change (JPI FACCE) and JPI Oceans. Interested in Joining the PS SFS as well as Agroecology, BlueBIO, One Health, Biodiversa, Chemical risk, circular biobased Europe, AMR, PAHW, Agriculture of Data.
Opportunity	Estonia is a small country compared to others but they have a strong record participating in many ERA-Nets. For them, the added value of collaboration on European level is clear. Not only does it bring immense economic advantage to pool resources, but also the research community gets new international contacts and can gain capacities and expertise not available on national level. At the same time, others can profit from the Estonian expertise and collaboration.
Good practices	General call rules should be flexible, leave some room for specific rules to the national annexes. Good experiences with gap funding.
Improvement	Timing of the funding: The last call should end early enough before the end of the programme to avoid that nobody takes care of the running project. Short projects of 1-2 year duration could also be a solution for the last call.
Public regional funder Finland	
Current situation	Regional funding mechanism.
Partnerships	Interest in SFS partnership

Opportunity	Long term perspectives (stakeholder agreements, thematic plans, etc.).
Improvement	Project based funding have a lack of synergies with other projects or no follow up. Lack of aligning national strategies with regional strategies.
Public regional funder France	
Current situation	Regional independence, own budget and strategy for food and agriculture.
Partnerships	Interest in SFS partnership
Opportunity	Quadruple helix and open call mechanism. Create / initiate the connection between (regional) stakeholders. Create a platform to share knowledge and adapt solutions between regions.
Good practices	Support young farmers and maintain regional capacity of food production Regional funding more for practical projects.
Public national funder Germany	
Current situation	No option to fund industry organisations.
Partnerships	Involved in: Agro-ecology, Agriculture of data, Animal health and welfare Interest in SFS partnership
Opportunity	Ask researchers what they perceive as bottlenecks.
Good practices	The Knowledge hub call of JPI HDHL, JPI FACCE and JPI OCEANS. Living labs (requires long research funding periods). Real common funding pot under CORE-Organic ERA-net, no problems with a ranking list, challenge to fund other countries with national money. Systems approach (ERA-net GAS and SUSAN and the knowledge hub of JPI FACCE MACSUR).
Public regional funder Italy 1	
Current situation	Most important funding sources are Horizon programs and Interreg. Also funding from regional and national funding.
Partnerships	?
Opportunity	Increase the number of participating countries in a consortium so knowledge can be shared on a larger scale.
Good practices	Good cooperation with neighbouring countries (production and distribution of local produced products)
Private/philanthropic funder Italy 1	
Current situation	The territory supports and promotes specific demands that preserve local traditions and knowledge (resilience). The area supports and promotes specific demands that preserve local traditions and knowledge (resilience). The foundation supports projects that ensure economic and developmental returns throughout the territory, especially in more remote and less developed areas.
Partnerships	Interest in participating in Mirror Groups
Opportunity	Strong connection with local realities is needed. Using a scientific approach to evaluate the effects of participatory research (education, family participation, etc.) and understand how much it can improve people's lifestyles. International research center on climate change impacts.
Good practices	Terranext: supporting start-ups operating in the bioeconomy sector. The aim was to support the most innovative realities at national level, creating interconnections with local scientific excellence and spreading the culture of open innovation. AGER enables networking among different research centers and between researchers and operators in the sector to improve innovation and competitiveness of the agribusiness system.
Private/philanthropic funder Italy 2	
Current situation	An association working throughout Italy to innovate the agrifood sector, promote shared projects and enhance the value of quality Made in Italy products. Consisting of Universities and banking foundations.
Partnerships	Interest in participating in Mirror Groups
Opportunity	Support the establishment of incubators in agribusiness to connect traditional knowledge and expertise with possible agricultural entrepreneurs. In this way, incubators have the ability to match supply and demand so entrepreneurs who have not the availability of land are still able to revive local production.
Good practices	Uniting research centers and specialized local producers to support and enhance small local quality production. This is accomplished through accompaniment and training to improve access to markets and innovative knowledge. Supporting quality short supply chains makes it possible to directly support the local area, enhancing its history, production process, product quality, preserving biodiversity and social context. it is useful to involve the banking system, for it to study appropriate instruments for different types of companies.
Improvement	It is necessary to convey awareness of the quality of productions to consumers so that the choices they make are conscious and informed and not dictated only by price. It is necessary to invest in good communication and awareness raising of local actors.

	A major difficulty small businesses face is related to obtaining funding to support innovative projects.
Public regional funder Italy 2	
Current situation	Funding from Horizon programs. Also ERDF, Interreg and Erasmus+ funding mechanisms. To lesser extend small funding from foundations.
Partnerships	Interest in SFS partnership
Opportunity	Develop a common 'terminology' since the food system is wide and people have different needs or interests.
Good practices	Circular economy projects (f.e. beer industry). The launch of a good practice manual for farmers and others in the agricultural process. Involvement of stakeholders from different sectors in projects to get versatile aspects to the projects.
Improvement	Processes need to be simplified in order to give small players also an opportunity to apply for funding. For example in Erasmus+, funding sections are quite strictly regulated, more flexibility is needed between programs and funding types. Find a mechanism to support small actors (farmers) to be more involved.
Public urban policy office Italy	
Current situation	The organisation receives funding from public administration, European projects and private grant making organisations.
Partnerships	?
Opportunity	Crowd fundings
Improvement	More focus on communication of the results in a accessible and clear way for the target audience. EU commission funding requires specific competencies and a level of expertise that are not always available to all actors and stakeholders.
Public national funder The Netherlands	
Current situation	The Dutch funder supports innovative research and development realised by public-private partnerships in this sector. They bring together stakeholders in a shared, consolidated innovation infrastructure to provide a financial Instrument to help consortia consisting of research organisations, knowledge institutes, companies and health foundations to realise their innovative idea.
Partnerships	No involvement
Good practice	The EUREKA calls are international calls set up between the Netherlands and other countries to fund research.
Public national funder Romania	
Current situation	Classic research calls can be funded. Possibility to have stakeholder involvement taking into account different rules.
Partnerships	Involved in: ERA4Health, Water4All, Transforming Health and Care Systems, Driving Urban Transitions, SMEs, and Biodiversa. Interest in SFS partnership and OneHealth AMR.
Opportunity	Virtual common pot
Good practices	Multidisciplinary approach in a resilience programme (systemic approach covering the topics health, food and soil). 5 projects which need to collaborate with each other. Clean Energy partnership.
Public national funder Switzerland	
Current situation	Involved in research funding by using the following mechanism: (1) small cash funding also for international research such as ERA-net, (2) informing the end-users (currently no budget), and (3) stakeholders like ministries and research institutes can fund.
Partnerships	Involved in: Horizon Europe agri food, egg, soil, agro scope Interested in partnerships since with little investment, one can have access to a large project.
Opportunity	Network of infrastructure (laboratories, technical equipment) inside Europe which can be used by other countries involved in the network. Build on former projects to reach the end-consumer or keep building new knowledge.
Good practices	ERA-net works well and has a human perspective. They have a national umbrella group for ministries in the form of a state secretariat which has an overview of 'hot topics' and will contact different ministries to contribute / participate.
Improvement	There is a focus on holistic research and answers, whilst funding agencies still function in silos. Broad thematic perspectives make it hard to define a specific subject / question to fund and makes it confusing for researchers to apply. Evaluation of the projects due to limited budget (personnel cost)
Public national funder Sweden	
Current situation	As a government research council for sustainable development the areas of activity include environment and agricultural sciences especially in the Area of Climate, Sustainable Spatial Planning and Food. Mainly scientific research can be funded; companies can only be funded in

	exceptional cases. Usually the principle investigator needs to have a PhD. But this situation is currently changing especially in the Area of food research where more and more “mixed calls” (RPO plus company) are carried out. There is also openness for new type of funding mechanisms such as “knowledge hubs” but no experiences in funding Living Labs until now. Research projects should normally run for 3 years.
Partnerships	Involved in three ERA-Net and 11 ERA-NET co-fund initiatives as well as seven Joint Programming Initiatives (JPIs), among them JPI Climate, Oceans, Water and Urban Europe. Will be involved in FS Partnership and also in PS Agroecology and Animal Health and Welfare.
Opportunity	Wants to see open calls; Possibility also for other types of Stakeholders/Actors, also non RPOs to apply. The opportunity to include social sciences more strongly is highly relevant.
Good practices	No direct examples, but broad open calls are essential. Preference for a 2-step procedure with short pre-proposals with low workload for the applicants (“project idea /concept note”) and a fully-fledged 2nd step.
Improvement	Quality of expert evaluation is essential. Flexibility is needed to ensure reaction to crises and rapidly changing topics and preferences.
Independent international body on Food Systems	
Current situation	This independent body consists of an international panel of experts on sustainable food systems to inform debates on food systems reform through policy-oriented research and direct with engagement with policy processes around the world. The panel brings together scientists, economists, nutritionists, agronomists, sociologists, practitioners from civil society and social movements.
Partnerships	Interest in participating in Mirror Groups (cannot receive grants from governmental or public institutions).
Opportunity	Take the role of civil society into consideration since they should participate more seizing the initiatives, developing deeper, wider and more effective collaborations than before. Funding should be used to support long-term actions (5 years). Building new partnerships to finance a quarter century of food system transformation. By the 2030s, allied funders move from short-term project grants to five-year funding cycles, double their funding at least every 10 years, and open up to experimental, speculative, intersectional, and readiness-building initiatives. Most importantly, they are prepared to use their money and influence to catalyse bigger financial shifts and policy changes
Good practices	Copenhagen and Gent are good examples where the policies were developed with clear objective and were followed by timely and tailor – made activities to achieve their aim. Paradesh (India) established a regional partnership with farmers and regional policymakers. Furthermore: EU Food Policy Coalition, Alliance for Agroecology in West Africa (3AO) and Agroecology Coalition (emerged from UNFSS).

Annex IV – Online Funders Forum Agenda 29th of November 2022

Objectives

- Share information about FOODPathS (including WP3) and the development of the SFS Partnership: specifically clarify the different roles, timelines and what is expected at which point of funders
- Collect experiences (good practices at various levels) and generate ideas to inspire future funding mechanisms in the SFS partnership to be able to address transdisciplinary, food systems oriented research topics
- Generate enthusiasm of funders to join network, map and future PS consortium?

What can we offer to funders?

- Information and clarification on what the FOODPathS CSA and the Sustainable Food Systems Partnership (SFSP) are and how they relate to each other
- Indicative time line and clarity on what is expected from them moving into the future partnership
- Inspiring examples for moving the funding landscape towards supporting more transdisciplinary, systemic research trajectories

What do we need from funders?

- Creative ideas for bringing change to the funding landscape
- Practical and inspiring examples for transdisciplinary (systemic) funding – to really support food systems transition
- Indicative interest for the future partnership, map of funders, funding network etc

Programme

Item no.	Time	Description	Facilitator/presenter	Remarks
1	09:30 – 09:40	Introduction - Welcome - Setting the scene/why are we here - Short introduction speakers/presenters	Nikola Hassan and Jasmina van Driel	Almost 80 people have signed up (on 17 th of November). Even if half attend, too many for introductory round., rationale for this event and the objectives of this morning, some “rules”/ organisational issues (everyone muted, please use chat for Questions, recording of meeting)
2	09:40 – 09:50	The SFS Partnership - what is it, goals and tentative time line, expectation from funders	Daniela Lüth, EC DG RTD (Policy Officer)	Where do we stand now with the SFSP and what will happen in the coming months, overview on indicative and total in-kind and in-cash contributions and which countries have indicated their interest; expectation towards the partnership; what is expected of funders the coming period; pre-published call and what does the consortium building process look like etc.
3	09:50 – 10:00	The CSA FOODPathS – what is it all about and how does it relate to the future SFS?	Hugo de Vries, INRAE (Coordinator FOODPathS)	FOODPathS and its goal and WPs, role division (between SCAR, what does CSA do, what will SFS consortium take up, promoting also the public consultation)
4	10:00 – 10:20	Q&A session	Hugo de Vries and Daniela Lüth facilitated by Jasmina van Driel or Nikola Hassan and chat moderator	As we are expecting more than 40 participants, Q&A will be done through the chat function
5	10:20 – 10:30	WP3 FOODPathS - Funders network and Map and first insights from interviews - Moving towards a funding landscape that supports systems transition and increased transdisciplinary research - Providing one or two teasers on good practices - Inform about future activities (e.g. Survey)	Nikola Hassan and Ivana Trkulja	Explanation of WP 3 + team, preparation of map (tour de table, on the map), promoting to those who are not around; tentative steps for next months; information about future survey; potentially including some highlights from interviews to serve as motivation for the interactive session. Here it should be emphasised that we would like them (the funders) to think of interesting examples of transdisciplinary funding and bring them to the physical funders forum

6	10:30 – 10:50	Q&A session	All from WP 3, depending on questions posed	
7	10:50 – 11:00	Short energy break		
8	11:00 – 11:50	<p>Group work – “Envisioning the future funding to support the transition of food systems”</p> <p>Group work in groups of 10 to 15 people (depending on registration). Maximum 6 groups.</p> <p>This should be framed as an “appetiser” or “food for thought” for the physical event in February 2023 – as we will not be able to go very deep into the topic due to limited time now.</p>	<p>Facilitators from WP 3 team:</p> <p>Group 1: Ivana Trkulja</p> <p>Group 2: Merete Studnitz</p> <p>Group 3: Nikola Hassan</p> <p>Group 4: Frank Hensgen</p> <p>Group 5: Giullia Lombardi</p> <p>Group 6: Jasmina van Driel</p> <p>Back-up: Valentina Amorese, Sara Scalabrin</p> <p>Please note that each group needs to appoint a note-taker, who will also report back to the plenary (not one of the facilitators).</p>	<p>Each group will get three questions, from which they can choose (or cover all three, depending on the wishes of the group):</p> <p>Overall assignment: Imagine we are in 2033 (future in 10 years). The Partnership SFS has been a great success and R&I played an important role to enable the transformation of our Food Systems to be sustainable, healthy and resilient and supporting a healthy and thriving European population. Please answer one, two or all of the following questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What changes are necessary - with regard to funding of research - to support this transformation through transdisciplinary research? (step out of your comfort zone, envisage the ideal world, think innovation?) - To determine what impact the SFS partnership has had in 10 years time please answer the following: What does “impact” mean for you? What does it mean for a transnational collaboration? What are points in the funding cycle where we can steer for impact (value and results from the projects and/ or the Partnership)? - Please provide examples of research projects with a multi-/inter-/transdisciplinary, wide (systems) focus that could contribute to this vision (think of different levels, national, regional, international and different types of projects, e.g. living labs, knowledge hubs, classic research projects and others)
9	11:50 – 12:20	Groups reporting back to plenary		Max. 2 to 3 minutes per group; total of 6 groups
10	12:20 – 12:30	Rounding up and next steps	Jasmina van Driel and Nikola Hassan	

Annex V – Physical Funders Forum Agenda 8th of February 2023, Brussels

Objectives

- To obtain updates from different actors regarding the process towards the Sustainable Food Systems Partnership (a.o. EC DG RTD, Proposal Coordinator ANR)
- To share and collect examples of Food Systems funding approaches
- To test a Food Systems funding approach on real-life topics

What can we offer you as a participant?

- Update about the Sustainable Food Systems Partnership preparations
- Inspiring exchanges with others on funding practices and on changing the funding landscape towards supporting more food systems research trajectories
- Co-creating future Food Systems oriented funding modes

What do we need from you as a participant?

- Your expertise and experience with regard to funding practices and Food Systems approaches
- Examples (from all scales: regional/national/EU/international) of how Food Systems transition can be supported through transnational R&I funding
- Willingness and openness to exchange on what worked and also what did not work

Item no.	Time	Description	Facilitator/presenter
0	10:30 – 11:00	Registration with coffee, tea and networking opportunity	
1	11:00 - 11:15	Opening and introduction*	Nikola Hassan, FZJ and Jasmina van Driel, ZonMw
2	11:15 - 11:25	The Sustainable Food Systems Partnership (SFSP)*	Guest speaker Daniela Lüth, DG RTD
3	11:25 - 11:32	Questions for clarification*	
4	11:32 - 11:42	SFS Partnership Consortium proposal process*	Guest speakers Claude Yven and Gilles Ferron, ANR
5	11:42 - 11:50	Questions for clarification*	
6	11:50 - 12:00	Examples of (Food) Systems funding and research approaches*	Nikola Hassan and Frank Hensgen, FZJ
7	12:00 - 12:10	Experiences and points of attention when trying to implement a (food) systems approach*	FOODPathS WP 3 team
8	12:10 - 12:30	Question and discussion round*	
9	12:30 - 13:15	Lunch break	
10	13:15 - 13:30	A Food Systems Approach in light of the Sustainable Food Systems Partnership*	Ivana Trkulja and Merete Studnitz, AU-ICROFS and Susanne Hansen AU-DCA
11	13:30 - 15:10	Operationalising a Food System approach in call mechanisms Interactive Group work – WP 3 team led by AU-ICROFS	Ivana Trkulja and Merete Studnitz, AU-ICROFS and Susanne Hansen, AU-DCA Groups will each work on a specific, fictive topic and develop a call description, selection criteria, devise monitoring and evaluation approaches and develop guidelines
12	15:10 - 15:30	Closing session	Nikola Hassan, FZJ and Jasmina van Driel, ZonMw
13	15:30 – 16:15	Drinks and networking	

*The plenary parts of the programme will be livestreamed through the following link:

<https://zonmw.zoom.us/j/98037119064?pwd=UzJwV2tqNHNFVnFCcm9ZUFJNcTA1UT09>

Passcode: 4@k9rpdE

Webinar ID: 980 3711 9064

Who are “we”?

We are the FOODPathS Work Package 3 team. Through the engagement of stakeholders across food systems, the FOODPathS project will create a “Prototype” of how the future Sustainable Food Systems Partnership could operate. Specifically Work Package 3 is focused on co-creating future funding mechanisms and strategies that can maximise the impact of Research and Innovation towards SFS by gathering experiences and expertise of a diverse group of funders. The following organisations and networks are represented in Work Package 3:

Name	Representatives	Type of Organisation	Country
Aarhus University - International Centre for Research in Organic Food Systems (AU-ICROFS) / representing CORE Organic network	Ivana Trkulja Merete Studnitz	Research Organisation	Denmark
Fondazione Cassa di Risparmio Delle Provincie Lombardie (Cariplo)	Valentina Amorese Sara Scalabrin	Philanthropic Organisation	Italy
Institute of Rural and Agricultural Development of the Polish Academy of Sciences (IRWIR PAN) / representing BIOEAST	Barbara Wieliczko Aleksandra Pawłowska Pawel Chmielinski	Research Organisation	Poland
Philanthropy Europe Association (Philea)	Giulia Lombardi	Philanthropic Organisation	Belgium
Research Center Jülich (FZJ)/ representing SUSFOOD2 network	Nikola Hassan Frank Hensgen	Research Organisation	Germany
Seinäjäki University of Applied Sciences (SeAMK) / representing ERIAFF network of regions	Terhi Junkkari Karri Kallio	Higher Education	Finland
The Netherlands Organisation for Health Research and Development (ZonMw) / representing Joint Programming Initiative a Healthy Diet for a Healthy Life (JPI HDHL)	Jasmina van Driel Bernadette Conrads	Funding Organisation	Netherlands

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